

CONCEPT ANALYSIS: ETHICAL SENSITIVITY IN PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE

Ihsanur Rahman^{*1}, Muhammad Ishtiaq², Bushra Sultan³

^{*1,2,3}Shifa College of Nursing, Shifa Tameer-e-Millat University, Pakistan

^{*1}ihsan2321@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Ihsanur Rahman

Abstract

Background: Ethical sensitivity (ES) is gaining increasing attention in healthcare due to its central role in guiding moral decision-making and shaping the quality of patient care. Despite its importance, ES lacks a consistent definition, and related terms are often used interchangeably, leading to conceptual ambiguity across professional disciplines.

Objective: The aim of this analysis to clarify the concept of ethical sensitivity in professional practice.

Design: A literature search was conducted using the descriptors “ethical sensitivity,” “moral sensitivity,” “ethical awareness,” and related terms in PubMed, CINAHL, Wiley Online Library, and Google Scholar. Literature published from 2009 onward was reviewed to capture current conceptual developments. A total of 41 sources from nursing, medicine, psychology, social sciences, business, dentistry, journalism, and engineering were included.

Research design: The eight-step procedure for concept analysis developed by Walker and Avant was employed to identify defining attributes, antecedents, consequences, model and related cases, and empirical referents of the concept.

Findings and discussion: The analysis resulted in a clear conceptual definition of ES. Critical attributes identified include moral perception, divided loyalties, awareness of ethical issues, interpretation of ethical situations, empathy and perspective-taking, and commitment to professional ethical standards. Key antecedents include knowledge of ethical codes, professional experience, and exposure to ethical dilemmas. Consequences include enhanced patient outcomes, strengthened professional integrity, and reduction of moral distress.

Conclusion: Ongoing refinement of the concept of ethical sensitivity is needed to strengthen its application in clinical practice. Further research and the development of standardized assessment tools are essential to support education, evaluation, and ethical competence among healthcare professionals.

Introduction

Ethical sensitivity (ES) may be defined as that which enables professionals to recognize, interpret, and respond appropriately to the concerns of those receiving professional services (González-de Paz et al., 2012). Healthcare professionals must have the ability to deal with

moral dilemmas, specifically in complex situations involving patient autonomy, confidentiality, and end-of-life decisions (Billings, 2011). In nursing, ES refers to the nurse's ability to identify the crucial nature of ethical practice and clinical action (Milliken, 2018). To respond ethically to a situation, an individual must possess the ability to

perceive and interpret events in a manner that facilitates ethical action (Van Der Zande et al., 2014). This requires a broad set of skills and techniques, including interpersonal sensitivity, such as perspective-taking, empathy for fostering connection, and the capacity to evaluate situations by anticipating potential outcomes (Robichaux, 2012).

Methodology

The concept of ES in professional practice will be analyzed using Walker and Avant's (1986) model. This model is most commonly used in nursing, and serves as the basis of analyzing core concepts of nursing and describe the entire process step by step (Bayrampour et al., 2016; Nuopponen, 2010; Walker & Avant, 2014). It helps scholars refine concepts, and supports the building of nursing knowledge. This model consists of eight steps which are: 1. Choose a concept for analysis, 2. Clarify the purpose or aim of the analysis, 3. Identify all potential uses of the concept, 4. Determine the defining characteristics or attributes of the concept, 5. Identify a model case that illustrates the concept with specific examples, 6. Identify related, borderline, contrary, and invented cases, 7. Determine the antecedents and consequences associated with the concept, 8. Define empirical referents that can be used to measure the concept (McEwen & Wills, 2018).

Selection of a Concept and its Significance in Nursing

The concept of ES selected for analysis due to its growing relevance in hospital settings, particularly in situations involving patients and their family members. During my previous clinical experience in the critical care unit, I observed that healthcare professionals frequently confronted ethical dilemmas related to decision-making, patient privacy, informed consent, and cultural sensitivity while interacting with patients and their attendants. These interactions often require a high degree of ES to ensure respectful, compassionate, and morally appropriate care.

The literature illustrates the importance of ES, which is essential for shaping the quality of patient care, fostering collaboration with the healthcare

team, and maintaining professional integrity (Huttunen, 2023). Despite its recognized importance, the ES lacks a standard definition, leading to inconsistent application in clinical practice and varied interpretations across different disciplines. The term "ethical sensitivity" previously referred to as "moral sensitivity" is defined as the capacity to distinguish right from wrong and to evaluate the potential impact of one's actions on others (Rest, 1982). This concept was later reframed as "ethical sensitivity" to better align with professional standards and codes of conduct (Bebeau et al., 1985). This shift highlights the growing need for nurses to engage in deliberate ethical decision making (Chen et al., 2021). ES is crucial for developing effective interventions, promoting ethical conduct, and assisting nurses in understanding their professional moral obligations in complex healthcare settings (Milliken, 2018).

Purpose/Aim of the Analysis

The purpose of this analysis is to explore and define the concept of ES in depth within professional practice. This aims to provide clear, structured definitions for readers and, through a comprehensive exploration of related concepts, will help distinguish the scientific and theoretical understanding of ES from ordinary uses. It will contribute to a more precise and practical application of ES in professional settings.

Literature Search

The literature search was done through PubMed, Wiley online library, CINAHL, and Google Scholars to explore the available literature on the use of ES in professional practice. Search terms used were "ethical sensitivity" OR "moral sensitivity" OR "moral" OR "ethical" AND "perception" OR "intuition" OR "professional practice." Using these terms, the search yielded 48,848 articles from the Wiley Online Library, 2,232 articles from PubMed, 144 from CINAHL, and approximately 283 from Google Scholar. The search focused on literature published from 2009 onward to capture the most recent developments in the field, considering that a similar foundational concept was published in 2008 (Weaver et al., 2008). The

studies included had clear definitions of ES, contributed meaningfully to concept analysis, were written in English, and had full-text versions available. The final sample included 41 articles and books from various fields, including nursing (18), social sciences (6), medicine (4), business (4), psychology (4), dentistry (2), journalism (2), and engineering (1). This diverse selection was intended to provide a well-rounded understanding of the concept from multiple disciplinary perspectives.

Definitions from Various Sources

Ethics

- The term "ethics" is derived from the Greek word "ethos," which means "character" (Baumlin & Meyer, 2018).
- Ethics is defined as "the study of what is morally right and wrong, or a set of beliefs about what is morally right and wrong" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023).
- "The principles of conduct governing an individual or a group" (Merriam-Webster dictionary).

Sensitivity

- "An ability to understand what other people need and be helpful and kind to them" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023).
- "Awareness of the needs and emotions of others" (Merriam-Webster Dictionary).

Professional

- "Relating to work that needs special training or education" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023).

Practice

- "Something that is usually or regularly done, often as a habit, tradition, or custom" (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023).

Ethical sensitivity

- ES is defined as the ability to make thoughtful and compassionate decisions in uncertain care situations by utilizing ethical guidelines, clinical experience,

academic knowledge, and self-awareness while anticipating potential outcomes and demonstrating the courage to take action (Shayestehfard et al., 2020).

Surrogate Terms

The terms which are interchangeably used for ES such as *moral character*, *moral judgment*, *moral empathy*, *moral sense*, *ethical consciousness*, *ethical awareness*, and *ethical perception* (Powerthesaurus, 2025); however, each carries a distinct meaning and should not be considered identical. Moral judgment focuses on decision-making, moral character emphasizes personal traits, and ethical awareness centers on recognizing ethical concerns. In contrast, ES uniquely integrates emotional attunement, situational understanding, and professional responsibility to guide ethical behaviors.

Identify all Possible Uses of the Concept

To avoid biases, uses of the concept should not be limited to a single discipline, all uses of the terms must be considered to know the real nature of the concept (Walker & Avant, 2013). This concept is explained from the perspectives of its use in the nursing profession, other disciplines (details mentioned below), and ordinary use.

Concept Use in Nursing

ES, as the first step in the decision-making process, equips nurses to identify ethical dilemmas and formulate appropriate responses. (Holloway, 2023). This concept has been studied within the framework of caring science, researchers focusing on its application in clinical practice, relationship to moral and ethical reasoning, and importance in guiding ethical decision-making and patient care (Holloway, 2023). Study in this area explored, how nurses experience and address ethical challenges (Holloway, 2023). ES involves identifying an ethical issue, demonstrating a secure, ethical, contextual, and intuitive comprehension of the patient's precarious situation, and understanding the ethical implications of decisions made on their behalf (Arries, 2020; Nelwati et al., 2019).

Milliken (2018) defined "ES as recognizing the fundamental ethical nature of clinical practices. It

is crucial for moral organizations to ensure the provision of good patient-centered care” (p. 2). A lack of ES can lead to ethically inappropriate care and violate professional obligations. Therefore, it is necessary for nurses to develop interventions and understand ethical practices” (Milliken, 2018, p. 3). In a similar study illustrated, ethically sensitive nurses can understand situations from different perspectives, actively seek information and demonstrate an awareness of patients emotions and responses for patient centered care (Ertuğ et al., 2014).

Use in Other Disciplines

A similar concept is used in many disciplines, including healthcare (medicine, psychology, and dentistry) and fields concerned with safeguarding public and private security, rights, and information (business, law, and journalism). Perspectives from these various disciplines were included to capture the full spectrum of meanings, interpretations, and applications of the concept in diverse contexts.

ES in medicine empowers physicians to identify and address ethical dilemmas in patient care settings. It underpins crucial aspects of clinical decision-making, such as respecting autonomy, promoting benefits, and resolving value conflicts. By enhancing communication, empathy, and professional judgment, ES fosters trust, improves the quality of care, and upholds moral integrity in complex medical situations (Kirilmaz et al., 2015). ES is examined from the perspective of psychology, recognizing ethical concerns related to patient confidentiality or informed consent (Reamer, 2018). In dentistry, ES refers to identify and address ethical issues in a manner, promotes both personal and professional growth, thereby encourage behavior that is socially and professionally responsible (Chughtai et al., 2019). In the context of social sciences, ES is the awareness of how one’s actions affect others (Friedman, 2017, p.1). In terms of business ethics, ES use for a company’s ability to recognize the moral implications of decisions, particularly regarding corporate social responsibility or ethical leadership (Reamer, 2018). It is a key factor in fostering effective corporate governance (Chan,

2012). In the law profession, ES is crucial for discerning the moral aspects inherent in legal decisions and client interactions. This sensitivity enables legal practitioners to adeptly navigate complex ethical dilemmas, harmonize justice with compassion, and maintain integrity while interpreting and applying legal principles in their work (Rohr, 2017). ES in journalism encompasses the recognition of the moral implications inherent in reporting, including respect for privacy, avoidance of harm, and assurance of accuracy (Ahmed, 2024).

Ordinary use

Generally, ES refers to an individual's ability to perceive and understand the moral issues in their surroundings (Robichaux, 2012). People may use the term informally to describe someone attuned to ethical considerations in daily life, for instance, recognizing actions that may cause harm to others (Robichaux, 2012).

Critical Attributes

The heart of the concept analysis is determining the defining attributes of a concept. Attributes that are frequently associated with the concept provide the reader or analysis with a broad insight (Walker & Avant, 2013). After reviewing the literature, the following attributes were identified.

Moral Perception

Moral perception is the ability to notice important details and patterns (cues, expressions awakening, and particularization). This helps professionals understand what clients need in different situations (Van Grunsven et al., 2023). Professionals often perform the technical aspects of their work without much reflection until a specific cue prompts them to do so (Van Grunsven et al., 2023). The professional aims to identify the origin and scope of the issue by exploring the client's perceptions of space, time and familiar experiences. The process of particularization is influenced by the clarity and availability of cues (Vough et al., 2013). Moral perception should embrace a broad and inclusive perspective. It should prioritize understanding over retribution, value dignified and nondiscriminatory care, and

be guided by the principles of love, justice, and solidarity (Gallagher, 2013).

Dividing Loyalties

Divided loyalties refer to internal conflict that arises when an individual feels torn between competing commitments to different people, groups, or values (Reamer, 2018). This often results in a sense of being pulled in multiple directions, making it difficult to fully dedicate oneself to any single entity or cause (Reamer, 2018). Divided loyalties occur when professionals face challenging decisions that involve conflicting responsibilities or interests (Womack, 2015). Navigating these situations requires careful reflection on the specific circumstances, including an honest assessment of the factors involved. Professionals must also examine their personal values, beliefs, and external influences that may affect their decisions (Wiltsher, 2021).

Awareness of Ethical Issues

It is one of the fundamental attributes of ES, the ability to recognize and understand ethical dilemmas in professional practice (Rahmani et al., 2023). This involves identifying situations in which moral or ethical considerations, such as patient autonomy, informed consent, or confidentiality, are present. Professionals with ES can differentiate ethical concerns, even when they are not apparent (Rahmani et al., 2023). Ethical awareness is crucial for recognizing the ethical implications inherent in all nursing actions and constitutes the initial step in moral decision-making (Milliken, 2017).

Interpretation of Ethical Situations

ES includes the ability to interpret and analyze ethical issues. This involves understanding the context of the situation, identifying relevant ethical principles, and evaluating the possible outcomes (Kögler, 2010). Professionals must apply critical thinking and ethical frameworks to comprehensively assess situations (Kögler, 2010).

Empathy and Perspective Taking

Empathy comprises two distinct but related components: perspective taking, the cognitive ability to understand another's viewpoint, and

empathic concern, the emotional capacity to feel compassion (Cojuharenco, 2015). A key characteristic of ES is considering the perspectives and emotions of those involved in ethical dilemmas, particularly patients and their families. ES ensures that decisions are made not only based on theoretical knowledge but also with an awareness of their emotional and psychological impacts (Longmire & Harrison, 2018).

Commitment to Professional and Ethical Standards

This concept is closely linked to adherence to professional codes of conduct and ethical standards. Professionals with a high level of ES do more than simply acknowledge these standards; they actively internalize and apply them in decision-making. By supporting their actions with core ethical principles, integrity, accountability, and trustworthiness in professional practice are promoted (Dehghani et al., 2015).

Model case

The model case should be a pure case and an instance of the concept. It could be a real-life example, constructed by you or found in literature (Walker & Avant, 1995, p. 42). The following case illustrates the use of ES in a clinical setting, highlighting its key attributes.

Afia, 60-year-old woman with advanced cancer, was admitted to the palliative care unit. Despite receiving high doses of pain management therapy, she experienced severe discomfort. During a private conversation with her Registered Nurse (RN) Sania, Afia expressed a desire to end her suffering and inquired about assisted suicide. Sania immediately recognized, this is not only a clinical issue, but a complex ethical issue involving autonomy, suffering, and the sanctity of life. Sania is aware that assisted suicide is legally prohibited and ethically contentious in her context and knows that any inappropriate response could breach legal and professional standards.

She experienced an internal conflict, torn between compassion for Afia's suffering, respect for her autonomy, and her professional duty to maintain ethical norms. Drawing on the ethical principles of autonomy, beneficence, and non-maleficence,

Sania thoughtfully considered respond in a manner that honored Afia's concerns without compromising her professional responsibilities. She listened empathetically, validated Afia's pain, and made her feel supported rather than judged. While Sania could not ethically or legally support assisted suicide, she acted in alignment with her professional code by collaborating with the multidisciplinary team to enhance Afia's palliative care, addressing not only her physical pain but also her emotional and spiritual distress.

Borderline case

A borderline case encompasses some, but not all, of the defining attributes of a concept (Walker & Avant, 1995, p. 43). Ms. Shazoo, a critically ill patient with advanced cancer, sought assistance in ending her life to alleviate unbearable pain. The attending nurse recognizes this ethical dilemma and comprehends the complexity of such requests. However, instead of fully adhering to legal and professional guidelines, the nurse refrains from consulting the healthcare team, seeking input from the hospital ethics committee or requesting legal guidance. Although the nurse is aware of the ethical implications, she does not undertake the necessary steps to comprehensively address the issue.

Contrary case

A contrary case is an example that does not include any of the defining elements of a concept (Walker, 2005). Sadia 42-year-old female patient admitted with end-stage liver failure. She expressed a desire to end her life due to severe complications and distressing symptoms. However, the nurse failed to acknowledge her emotional suffering or explore alternative care options. This lack of sensitivity and ethical considerations demonstrates a significant gap in patient-centered care, where neither her wishes nor her need for compassionate support were adequately addressed.

Antecedents

"Antecedents are those events or incidents that must occur or be in place before the occurrence of the concept" (Walker & Avant, 2013). Several key

antecedents contribute to the development of ES in healthcare.

One fundamental antecedent is the knowledge of ethical codes and standards. Healthcare professionals must have a strong understanding of ethical guidelines, institutional policies, and legal regulations to effectively recognize and address ethical dilemmas (Inc, 2023). Without this foundational knowledge, the ability to perceive ethical issues would be significantly impaired.

Another critical antecedent is exposure to ethical dilemmas. ES develops when healthcare providers encounter challenging situations involving conflicting ethical principles, such as autonomy versus beneficence (Schermer, 2013). These real-world experiences shape their ability to identify and respond to ethical concerns in the future.

Moreover, professional experience and training are crucial preconditions. Healthcare workers receive specialized training in ethical decision-making and structured instruction to better prepare them to handle difficult moral dilemmas (Lo, 2012). Clinical practice experience helps them become more ethically conscious, which helps them make wise and kind judgments.

Consequences

According to Walker and Avant (1995), consequences refer to events or incidents that arise due to the occurrence of a concept. The consequences of ES can significantly impact both patient care and the well-being of healthcare professionals.

One major consequence of ES is to improve patient outcome. Healthcare providers demonstrate ES to make decisions align with patients' values and needs, lead to enhance patient satisfaction and improved health outcomes. ES allows nurses to provide care that respects patients' dignity and preferences (Stiggelbout et al., 2015).

Another significant outcome is strengthened professional integrity. ES cultivates trust and fortifies the relationship between healthcare providers and patients, ensuring that professionals in the field remain dedicated to ethical decision making. This commitment reinforces core professional values such as honesty, respect, and patient advocacy.

However, a lack of ES can result in moral distress and burnout among healthcare professionals. When healthcare providers encounter ethical dilemmas but feel constrained by institutional or personal limitations, they may suffer from emotional exhaustion.

Conclusion

This analysis clarifies the concept of ES to support its practical application in healthcare, particularly in nursing, where professionals often face complex ethical dilemmas. ES involves both emotional and intellectual engagement in patient care. By reviewing the existing literature, identifying key attributes, and offering a clear definition, this analysis deepens the understanding of ES.

Advanced practice nurses must recognize the role of ethical awareness in patient care and in decision-making. ES involves recognizing and addressing ethical issues while upholding the patient’s autonomy and dignity. When patients cannot express their wishes, healthcare professionals must rely on ethical principles and understand patient values. ES requires empathy, integrity, sound judgment, and open communication with patients and families to ensure that care aligns with the patient's best interests. Strengthening ES enhances ethical decision-making, improves patient outcomes, and fosters a supportive care environment.

Figure1 Model of the dimensions of the concept of ethical sensitivity in professional practice.

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